

THE PERIOD OF AMIRATES AND KHANATES IN TURKISTAN: A HISTORICAL OVERVIEW OF PUBLIC VETERINARY SERVICES

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Abstract. *The article examines the state of animal husbandry in Turkestan in the period of the emirates and khanates, as well as the integration of folk veterinary science and medical science in the care and treatment of livestock in a historical perspective. The impact of political, social and economic instability in the emirates and khanates on livestock and veterinary services, as well as the role of livestock and veterinary services in the public administration system are objectively highlighted.*

Keywords: *Bukhara Emirate, Khiva Khanate, Kokand Khanate, Kushbegi, Mirakhur, Russian chronicles, political and economic instability, famine, acute infectious diseases, plague, smallpox, anthrax, "desertification", "village life", influence of the first and second Renaissance, manuscript sources.*

In the history of the peoples of Central Asia, the era of emirates and khanates occupies a special place and has unique features. Because during the reign of Amir Temur and the Temurids, the peoples of this vast land were united around a single centralized state, and after the collapse of the Temurid dynasty, it was replaced by the dynasty of the Sheibani Khans (1510-1599). After a century of Sheibanid rule, the political system of the Ashtarkhanid dynasty (1599-1753) was established among Uzbek dynasties, and from the second half of the 18th century, a new Mangid dynasty founded an emirate in Bukhara (1753-1920). In Khorezm, as a result of the fall of the Timurid dynasty in 1512, a new khanate was formed - the Khiva Khanate, which also disintegrated in 1920. In 1710, the Ming dynasty seized power in Kokand as part of the Ashtarkhanid Khanate, and the Kokand Khanate was created, which lasted until 1876. Frequent changes of dynasties in the emirates and khanates of Central Asia had a profound impact on the socio-political and economic situation of the country.

During the reign of the khanates and emirates, the country experienced famine, poverty, the decline of the Great Silk Road due to internecine wars and an unstable economic situation, which led to the frequent occurrence of dangerous infectious and harmful epizootics, epidemiological and exotic diseases that killed countless people and caused a catastrophe for animals. Infectious diseases common in neighboring countries often begin to spread in our country. In particular, in the 15th-17th centuries, epizootics of acute infectious diseases such as anthrax, cattle plague, sheep and goat pox, which occurred in Russia and a number of European and Asian countries, caused great material and economic damage. Russian chronicles report that in the 15th-17th centuries, anthrax was widespread in Russia, first as an epizootic affecting farm animals, and then as an epidemic causing great distress among people. This situation spread to the countries of Central Asia, Siberia and Europe neighboring Russia.

In 1608, the Russian chronicle writes, in the Dnieper region of Belarus and other neighboring countries, rabies spread first to dogs, then to farm cattle, and then to people, causing

great damage. People's lives were partially saved by immediately cauterizing the bite site with a hot iron. This disease quickly spread throughout Central Asia, mainly in the deserts of Desht-i-Kipchak.

According to Russian chronicles, the plague first spread to Russia in 1625, affecting cattle, and in 1677, an epizootic disease, pneumonia (peripneumonia), spread among the cattle, causing great material damage. Let us recall that 363 heads of cattle were killed in the royal estate of Izmailovo, and the total material damage to the royal household amounted to 1,000 silver sums. In addition, according to a document from the archives of the Ministry of Justice of Russia, in 1643, a horse died from an unknown disease on the prince's farm near Novorossiysk, that is, "all the horses died in the boyar's yard and in the "peasant yard", and this disaster was repeated every ten years in the peasant farm and in the prince's estates. The main signs of this disease (probably anthrax - S.Zh.) - the same information indicates - "Their bag is all swollen, and from this they die" or "In bags and on chest there were ulcers," he says. In 1665, the country experienced epidemics and epizootics of infectious diseases similar to those in Central Asia, causing great damage to the population and livestock.

For this reason, this livestock farming was not only important for the domestic economy, but also had commercial value, played a significant role in the development of foreign trade with foreign countries. Considering the significant material losses caused by the negative consequences of infectious diseases, the Russian state takes measures to combat epizootics and epidemic diseases, adopts special regulations, creates special administrative and medical bodies in the system of public administration. There is no historical evidence that any measures were taken against not only zoonotic but also epidemic infectious diseases that occurred on the territory of the Russian state and its border territories, as well as in Central Asia. However, it is quite likely that these diseases constantly occurred in Khorezm, Maverannahr, Dasht-i-Kyichok and other regions of Central Asia, causing great material and moral damage to people and animals, which is reflected in Russian chronicles, but not recorded in local khanates and emirates, and no measures were taken against them. Detailed information about this is contained in the letters of Abdulgazi Bakhodir Khan, Khan of Khorezm, and Ivan Fedetev, Russian ambassador to Khorezm. Khorezm Khan Abdulgazi Bahadir Khan wrote that, as a historian of Khorezm in the 17th century, it occurred to me to write down history, since historical chronology - chronicles - until that time were almost completely absent from the written documents of the Khorezm khans, or were not written, - he wrote in the books "Shajara Turk" and "Shajari Tarokima".

At the end of the 16th century, some changes occurred in nomadic cattle breeding, the term "village resident" appeared, as well as the colloquial terms "dikhnishin" (sedentary) and "sachronishin" or "sakhroshin" (nomadic). The term "village resident" referred to the nomadic population, which gradually turned their winter dwellings into permanent places of residence.

The agriculture of Khiva Khanate was considerably weaker than that of Bukhara Khanate, and the majority of the population of Khiva Khanate were nomadic cattle breeders. "In the lands of Jurgen (Yurgen)," writes Tsar Mikhail's ambassador Ivan Khokhlov, "there are few settlements, and all the people are nomads". In the famous work "Shajaray Turk" by Abdulgazi Bahadir Khan, according to the author, "nomads come to Khiva in the winter to provide themselves with bread, and in the spring they return to their places to pasture their sheep and lambs; "since there are no pastures around Khiva, as soon as they sprout, they move to the places

where the tribes live". Nomadic and semi-nomadic peoples used folk veterinary medicine to prevent and treat various livestock diseases and were skilled cattle breeders. Although Khorezm had more land for agriculture than the neighboring regions inhabited by Karakalpaks and nomadic Uzbeks, there was a shortage of pasture for livestock. Thus, Karakalpaks bordered on the north with Kazakhs, who in turn bordered on the south with Russians and Tatars, and trade relations had been established between them since ancient times (via the Great Silk Road), with Kazakhs playing the role of intermediaries. At the same time, constant trade relations with livestock products, fisheries, agriculture and handicrafts continued, and they participated with their products in fairs in Russia. Such active, constant bilateral contacts created ample opportunities for the mutual spread of sudden epidemics and epizootics.

Those traveling from Central Asia to Russia were controlled and checked at strict state control posts, while those traveling from Russia were subject to only political control by border guards, since there was no state control or special bodies in the emirates and khanates in Central Asia, and there was no need for veterinary inspection. In the political system of governing the country in the emirates and khanates, the state and its constituent authorities were governed exclusively by the khan, which created certain negative situations.

The governing system lacked some branches of power in the fields of science, culture, art, medicine, veterinary science, which were important for the state and society. "Mirahur" was a prestigious position in the palace, and his job was to be responsible for the horses belonging to the palace. None of the lower ranks up to the khan were involved in the management and control of the medical and veterinary service; only doctors and veterinarians from the people worked independently.

Famine and crop failure occurred during the reign of the Khan of Khorezm Abdulgazi Bahadir Khan. "A donkey's head cost forty or fifty coins, but it was never found". This historical information was provided by the Russian ambassador Vasily Daudov, who returned to Russia from Khiva in 1677: "There was no money for aid, there was no bread, there were no horses, and because of wars and internal strife, we bought bread and all kinds of food in Bukhara and Khiva at very high prices". This indicates that an economic crisis had occurred. We will provide more historical information on this matter. In particular, according to the historian Munis, in the second half of the 18th century, the supreme power in Khiva often changed - the "game of khans" was in full swing, and during the reign of one of these "khans", "Jahangir Khan", in five fortresses (in Khiva Khanate) famine began and (the population) turned into dogs and ate donkeys, sold their children to Kazakhs and thus supported themselves. For this reason, many Uzbeks and Sarts ... went to the Aral Sea and Bukhara. Another historian, Khoja Samandar Termizi, in his work "Dastur al-muluk" said: "During famine in Samarkand region, extreme difficulties arose when it reached its last limits, and not a single class of the population had barley or wheat bread" ... When the flames of hunger burned in the hearts of the unfortunate people, they were ready to give their lives for bread everywhere, (but) no one " was able to do this", he said, describing the social and economic situation.

Another story about political decline is noteworthy, written by the 17th century historian Makhmud ibn Wali and the historian Khoja Samandar Termizi, describing the consequences of continuous inter-khan wars. In particular, he writes about the situation in the city of Karshi: "By the will of fate, in the year one thousand one hundredth (1689), the smiles on the faces of happy people disappeared due to the small amount of food necessary to sustain their lives... The water

in the large rivers, due to their weakness, did not reach anywhere, like orphans: the wind filled them with dust and sand instead of water... springs and ponds... dried up due to drought and the subsequent famine and crop failure not only of people but also of livestock. Grief is a sign that a great disaster has come". It should also be noted that the combination of military campaigns, natural conditions and the emergence of infectious diseases often led to their spread throughout the country, causing major disasters. For example, in the early 16th century, when Shaybani Khan captured Samarkand from Babur Mirza, the winter was extremely severe and some disease spread, causing hundreds of thousands of people to die in Samarkand, Kesh, Karshi, Bukhara and other places in Transoxiana region, and livestock were slaughtered. Countless people died as a result of "some disease".

Although, in Central Asian khanates, medicine, traditional medicine and veterinary science were not given due attention in the system of state power, the influence and role of achievements in this field during the periods of the first and second Renaissance in the life of the peoples of Central Asia were strong. Veterinary specialists among the people had a special role in the practical development of veterinary science, combining their treatment with the expediency of the veterinary service. Although the madrasah was small, in the 16th-18th centuries many dedicated scientists and specialists studied there, who combined medical and veterinary activities. They showed dedication in protecting not only people, but also livestock from epizootic, epidemiological, zoonothropotic infectious diseases, in protecting the material well-being of the people. We will dwell on the activities of some of them in the field of medicine, traditional medicine and veterinary science.

One of them was Ali ibn Mukhammad al-Khwarizmi al-Kubrawi (lived in the 16th century), who worked mainly at the court of Nawruz Akhmad (Barak) (1544-1552) during the reign of Shaybani Khan (1500-1510) and his successors. Although he was one of the followers of the prominent dervish group of the Kubrawiyya order of his time, he was also a man well versed in the science of folk medicine, especially scientific veterinary medicine. Four of his works have survived to this day, the most notable of which is *Kitab Saidiya* (Book of Hunting). This book is specifically devoted to the science of veterinary medicine. It is based on the traditional medical practices of the peoples of the country, including Ibn Sina and Abu Rayhan Beruni, as well as the opinions and observations of the famous imam Burhaniddin Marghinani (died 1197) and a number of other representatives of medicine who preceded him. This book, which is directly related to veterinary science, discusses the requirements of the Sharia (fatwa) regarding domestic animals, the procedure for caring for them, types of wild animals and birds, the consumption of their meat (which Muslims eat), types of food. It also describes the recommended (cleanliness) and prohibited (most of them due to the risk of epidemics) types of food, as well as the procedure for hunting. The book consists of an introduction, fifteen chapters and a conclusion.

The following manuscripts from the 18th and 19th centuries contain valuable historical information about the problems of traditional veterinary medicine in the country, as well as their authors, and also contain important information about the types of livestock and poultry, their various diseases and the level of use of veterinary services based on traditional medicine in their treatment. Such rare manuscripts include "Ajayib al-Makhlūqat wa Gharayib al-Yagdat" and "On the order of handling birds", "The Book of Hunting" by Ali ibn Mahmud al-Khwarizmi al-Kubrawi and many others of great historical significance. Primary sources are of great

importance in creating the history of veterinary science in Uzbekistan. It will not be a mistake to say that until now there has been virtually no scientific research or in-depth study of the above-mentioned rare manuscripts, as well as their authors or calligraphers who translated them from Greek, Sanskrit (ancient Indian language), Arabic and Arabic-Persian.

Among the Shaybanid khans was Mullah Muhammad Yusuf al-Kahhal (lived in the 16th century), a folk healer who worked at the court of Abdullatif Khan (1567-1572) and the ruler of Samarkand, Sultan Said (1567-1572). He was known for his work in treating eye diseases, crises and uncertainties in diseases, and the appearance of patients. He was a skilled physician who treated patients according to their condition, pulse, and temperature. His first work is called *Zubdat al-Kahholin* (The Doctor of the Eye) and consists of an introduction and four chapters. In the treatise, he relies on the works of ophthalmologists who preceded him (who conducted experiments on animals to treat people) to help his teachers, brothers, and the people. He gives information about the causes of the widespread prevalence of eye diseases in his time, the widespread prevalence of eye diseases in black cattle and small cattle, as well as the methods and medicines for its treatment, based on the recommendations of familiar doctors knowledgeable in medical science. His second work is called "Tahqiq al-Hummiyat" ("The Study of Fevers"). This brochure consists of two parts, the first part of which discusses the causes, symptoms and methods of treating fever; the second part explains in detail the crisis of the disease and its types, drawing attention to the fact that its aspects related to animals were verified in practical experiments. The author recalls that when writing his works, he relied on the advice of his predecessors and his teacher Mawlana Mir Kanon.

The third treatise of the author is called "Treatise on the study of the pulse and urine of patients". This work was written using the many years of experience of the doctor and the works of representatives of Eastern medical science. It consists of two parts: the first part is dedicated to the pulse. It focuses on detecting diseases based on pulse patterns, diseases, seasons, people, nature (animals) etc. and the second part focuses on detecting diseases based on urine.

Another prominent figure in the science of critical medicine was Muhib Ali Farghani (d. 1581), who was the Governor of Delhi during the reign of Babur Jalaluddin Akbar Shah (1556-1605). He wrote a work called *Boznoma* (Book of Falcons), which consists of 61 chapters and is a medical treatise that identifies the species of hunting birds and treating them if they fall ill. In his work, he discusses falcons, birds in general, their care, and choosing the right breed for treatment. provided detailed information. He provided useful information on the methods and medicines for treating sick birds.

A 55-chapter treatise on horses, *Farasnoma*, written during the reign of Shah Jahan, a prominent member of the Babur dynasty, depicts horses in over 29 miniatures. It contains information on the study of horses, identifying good and bad traits, and treating diseases.

During the reign of Akbar Shakh, he paid great attention to science, like his grandfather, and many scientists, experts in medicine and folk healers gathered at his court. At the court of the Great Mughals, including during the reign of Akbar Shakh, many representatives of our country worked, seeking refuge in their homeland, in Central Asia, and finding protection from the Mughals from the oppression of restless khanates. Their works reached their homeland. Among them, the doctor Dawai al-Gilani, Arab Najafi, the doctor Darwish and dozens of other scientists were engaged in science, including medicine and veterinary science.

The author of the work "Favoyidu-l-inson" ("Charity for People") (2514-r), stored in the manuscript collection of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, is the great scientist of medicine, Hakim Dawai al-Gilani, who lived in the 16th century and worked at the court of Akbar Shakh (in India). The uniqueness of this work, dedicated to medical science, is that it is written in a poetic style, with Arabic or Persian names of medicinal plants, minerals and products of animal origin, indicating the diseases for the treatment of which they are used. Including deer antlers - for intestinal ulcers, hemoptysis, duck fat - for pain relief, chicken, beef brain - for scurvy, wild pigeon blood - for eye ulcers, donkey (wild ass) - for joint pain, eye pain, spots on the face, kidney pain. It contains information about the healing properties of black cumin in the stomach, desert acacia beans - a remedy for diarrhea, brains and crane meat - a remedy for blindness, as well as hundreds of other fruits and plants.

Another representative of medical science, known in Central Asia, is Ibn Kuglik-biy, also known as Muhammad Salih, who lived in the 16th century. His work "Risaali Hikmat" ("Treatise on Wisdom") is aimed at the treatment and prevention of parasitic helminthic invasive diseases that cause great material and economic damage to agriculture, fisheries and poultry farming.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the scientific study of historical data, we see the negative impact of socio-political and economic instability during the period of the emirates and khanates on medical and veterinary services, as well as on all other areas. Nevertheless, scientists who worked together in the service of medicine and folk veterinary medicine, the palaces of emirs and khans (many thousands of horses and cattle for the army), ordinary doctors and skilled specialists in their field - livestock breeders, managed to prevent and treat many diseases found in animals. The fact that our spiritual heritage associated with veterinary medicine has been poorly studied from a scientific point of view places a huge responsibility on historians and scientists in this field.

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